

Notes on the Nycteribiidae (Diptera) of Viet Nam

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A checklist of Nycteribiidae from Viet Nam consisting of 16 species of 6 genera is presented, 9 species are recorded for the first time.

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Introduction

The suprafamily Nycteribiidae is included in the superfamily Hippoboscoidea together with Glossinidae, Hippoboscidae and Streblidae. These families of Diptera are often called in literature by the common name Pupipara because of adenotrophic viviparity that is characteristic for all their species. The Nycteribiidae flies are known to be parasites of the bats only. They often have a high degree of host specificity and therefore their species diversity depends on the diversity of fauna of the bats.

The checklists of Nycteribiidae for many areas of Oriental realm consist of 20—30 species and apparently are complete enough. However, recently the checklist on these flies from Viet Nam was restricted by 3 species only (Maa, 1975).

The study of materials collected in Vu Quang Nature Reserve, Ha Tinh Province increased the number of Viet Nam Nycteribiidae up to 7 species (Farafonova, Borisenko, in litt.).

This note is based on the study of materials collected in March – April 1999 (leg. Kruskop) in Quang Binh Province (District Minh Hoa, Ce Boang) and also some materials from several locations of Viet Nam collected in 1985—1987 (leg. G. Kuznetsov) and 1997 (leg. Borisenko).

A total of 293 specimens of Nycterebiidae collected from more than 200 bats have been examined and now the checklist of Nycteribiidae consists of 16 species that significantly improves our knowledge of their fauna in Viet Nam.

Checklist of Nycteribiidae of Viet Nam

Subfamily Nycteribiinae

1. *Nycteribia dentata* Theodor, 1967

Material. 2 ♂, 2 ♀, from *Myotis siligorensis*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999; 1 ♂, from *Myotis (Leuconoe) longipes*, the same location; III—IV.1999;

2 ♂, 1 ♀, from *M. (L.) longipes*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 1 ♂, 5 ♀, from *M. (L.) longipes*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 1 ♂, from *M. (L.) longipes*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 2 ♂, 1 ♀, from *M. (L.) longipes*, the same location, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Nepal, on *Myotis (Leuconoe) longipes*.

2. *Phthiridium burmense* (Theodor, 1968)

Material. 1 ♂, from *Rhinolophus* sp., Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999; 1 ♀, from *Rhinolophus* sp., the same location, III—IV.1999; 1 ♂, from *Rhinolophus* sp., the same location, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Burma, on *Rhinolophus subbadius*, *Hipposideros lankadiva*.

3. *Ph. curvata* (?) (Theodor, 1967)

Material. 1 ♀, with *Hipposideros larvatus*, island Con Dao, 7.04.1987.

Distribution. Viet Nam, New Guinea, on *Hipposideros* sp.

4. *Ph. euxestum* (Speiser, 1901)

Material. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, from *Hipposideros armiger*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999; 1 ♂, from *H. armiger*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 1 ♀, from *H. armiger*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 2 ♂, 3 ♀, from *H. armiger*, the same location, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Burma, on *Hipposideros armiger*.

5. *Ph. fraternum* (Theodor, 1967)

Material. 1 ♂, from *Rhinolophus pearsoni*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999; ♂♂, ♀♀, from *Rh. affinis*, *Macroglossus sorbinus*, *Hipposideros armiger*, Vu Quang, VIII—IX.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Malaya, Thailand, on *Hipposideros* sp., *Cynopterus* sp.

6. *Phthiridium* sp. [sp. n.]

Material. 4 ♂, 2 ♀, from *Hipposideros larvatus*, island Phuong Hoang, 26.03.1987.

7. *Basilis brevipes* (Theodor, 1956)

Material. 1 ♀, from *Hypsugo pulveratus*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, on *Hypsugo imbricatus*, *Tylonycteris pachypus*.

8. *B. eileenae* Scott, 1936

Material. 3 ♀, from *Murina cyclotis*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Burma, on *Murina cyclotis*.

9. *B. magnocula* (Schuermans Stakhoven, 1942)

Material. ♂♂, ♀♀, from *Myotis horsfieldi*, *M. siligorensis*, Vu Quang, VIII.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Java, Moluccas, on *Myotis horsfieldi*, *Scatophilus kuhli*.

10. *B. majuscula* (Edwards, 1919)

Material. ♂♂, ♀♀, from *Pipistrellus javanicus*, Vu Quang, VIII.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Indonesia, Java, Sumatra, Philippines, on *Pipistrellus javanicus*, *Tylonycteris pachypus*.

11. *B. royllii* (Westwood, 1835)

Previous records. (Maa, 1975).

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Burma, Malaya, Sri Lanka, on *Tylonycteris pachypus*, *Scatophilus kuhli*.

Subfamily Cyclopodinae

12. *Eucampsipoda inermis* Theodor, 1955

Material. 2 ♂, 3 ♀, from *Rousettus leschenaulti*, Thai Nguen (=Bac Thai), 3.07.1985.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Thailand, Java, Philippines, New Guinea, on *Rousettus amplexicaudatus*, *Eonycteris spelaea*.

13. *E. latisterna* Schuurmans Stekhoven, 1938

Material. 51 ♂, 19 ♀, from *Rousettus leschenaulti*, Thai Nguen, 3.07.1985; ♂♂, ♀♀, from *Eonycteris speraea*, Vu Quang, VII.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Burma, Java, Indonesia, on *Rousettus* spp., *Tylonycteris pachypus*.

Previous records. (Maa, 1975).

14. *E. sundaica* Theodor, 1955

Material. 3 ♂, 1 ♀, from *Eonycteris spelaea*, Minh Hoa, Ce Boang, III—IV.1999; 6 ♂, from *E. spelaea*, the same location, III—IV.1999; 1 ♀, from *E. spelaea*, the same location, III—IV.1999.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Burma, Thailand, Malaya, Sumatra, Philippines, on *Eonycteris spelaea*, *Cynopterus sphix*.

15. *Cyclopodia horsfieldi* de Meijere, 1899

Material. ♂♂, from *Megaerops niphanae*, Vu Quang, IX.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, Thailand, Cambodia, Malaya, Java, Andaman, Indonesia, Philippines, Timor, on *Pteropus* spp., *Acerodon jubatus*, *Rousettus amplexicaudatus*.

16. *Leptocyclopodia ferrarii* (Rondani, 1878)

Material. 1 ♀, from *Cynopterus sphinx*, Hanoi, 25.09.1986; ♂♂, ♀♀, from *C. sphinx*, *Myotis siligoensis*, *M. muricola*, Vu Quang, VIII.1997.

Distribution. Viet Nam, India, Sri Lanka, Java, Burma, Thailand, Malaya, Sumatra, on *Cynopterus* spp.

Previous records. (Maa, 1975).

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